

Improving Peanut Ball Use: A Quality Improvement Project

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Project Purpose

Increase utilization of the peanut ball device in nulliparous, term, singleton, vertex (NTSV) laboring women and to reduce labor hours by implementing an instructional video course and poster display on the intrapartum unit.

Labor hours = The duration of time between the start of regular uterine contractions leading to cervical change and the birth of the baby.

Background

- Maternal morbidity and health care costs increase with cesarean section (CS) births
- NTSV CS rate at project site above quality standard of 23.9%
- Labor length is a leading cause of primary CS
- Peanut ball use in labor associated with shorter labors and lower risk of CS
- Registered nurse (RN) staff inconsistently use peanut ball with no formal staff education on peanut ball use
- Nursing support in labor improves birth outcomes

Methods

Design

- Quality improvement project

Setting

- Labor and delivery unit in a birthing hospital in southern California
- 250 births/month
- 70 labor and delivery RNs on staff
- Certified nurse midwife (CNM) and physician (MD) attend births

Data Collection

- RN peanut ball knowledge survey pre- and post-education
- Total labor hours for NTSV women using peanut balls collected via chart audit
- Peanut ball count for NTSV women recorded via chart audit

Project Implementation

- Peanut ball video course, poster display of peanut ball positions, RN peanut ball champions

Analysis

- Descriptive statistics, Spearman Correlation analysis, ANOVA, paired *t*-test, two-tailed samples *t*-test, McNemar's Chi-square test, Chi-square test of independence, control chart

Key Findings*

Due to Covid-19 restrictions, these results are based on fictitious data

- RN peanut ball knowledge improved post-education
- Increased number of peanut balls employed daily
- NTSV women using peanut balls experienced shorter labors

Limitations*

- Project by proxy only
- Small sample size
- Limited external validity

Conclusions

- Virtual nursing education is possible and has advantages not offered in the traditional classroom
- Obstetric nurses are committed to seeking information and guidance on nursing interventions to assist their laboring patients
- Nurses are ideally suited to lead and manage quality improvement projects

(screen shot from peanut ball educational video)

Framework - IHI's Model of Improvement

Adapted from Langley et al. (2009)

1. What are we trying to accomplish?

Improved utilization of the peanut ball and decrease in NTSV labor hours

2. How will we know that a change is an improvement?

Higher numbers of peanut balls placed and shorter NTSV labors

3. What changes can we make that will result in an improvement?

Formal instruction via educational video with poster review and RN champion support

NTSV Peanut Ball Use Control Chart*

- Pre-Project 1.6 PBs used/day
- Post-Project 2.4 PBs used/day
- Post-education, *shift* on day 51

